

GIS Application in Multi-Criteria Evaluation of Urban Riverfront Redevelopment

Dora Ivančan^{1,}, Sanja Gašparović¹, Ana Mrđa¹, Marija Premužić Ančić²*

¹ Department of Urban and Spatial Planning and Landscape Architecture, Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb, Croatia, divancan@arhitekt.hr, sgaspar@arhitekt.hr, amrda@arhitekt.hr

² ASK Atelier, d.o.o. Zagreb, Croatia, marija.premuzic@ask.hr

* corresponding author

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20408313

Abstract: The redevelopment of port and industrial areas along urban riverfronts represents a complex spatial intervention with multiple physical (spatial), functional, and environmental impacts. Although such transformations are a frequent topic in contemporary research and urban planning practice, their evaluation is most often conducted based on isolated sectoral indicators, without a comprehensive assessment of spatial changes and their relationship to the broader urban context. This paper presents a methodological contribution to the development of a multi-criteria evaluation framework for urban riverfront redevelopment by using a Geographic Information System (GIS). The research is conducted from an urban planning perspective and focuses on identifying and spatially analysing a selected set of criteria that describe changes in built structure, land use, transport connectivity, and the accessibility of public spaces. The analysis encompasses both the transformed area and its relationship to the adjacent urban fabric. The methodological framework is tested on selected examples of riverfront redevelopment in European cities of Nijmegen and Linz to examine the applicability of GIS-based spatial indicators within a multi-criteria evaluation context. The results represent a step toward the development of a comprehensive evaluation method to support evidence-based decision-making in sustainable urban planning and riverfront regeneration.

Keywords: sustainable waterfront planning; urban transformation; spatial analysis; Nijmegen; Linz.

1 Introduction

Port and industrial areas have historically been closely linked to riverfront locations, as waterways provided essential infrastructure for transport, trade, and production. Consequently, these functions have occupied some of the most valuable and strategically important urban areas. However, as industrial processes and logistics systems have evolved, many large cities have relocated port and industrial activities to peripheral zones with greater accessibility and capacity (Mann 1973). In smaller riverine cities, such relocation is often constrained by spatial, economic, and infrastructural limitations, making it impractical, costly, and potentially detrimental to local economic and social stability (Moccia 2012).

Despite these constraints, the need to adapt such areas to contemporary urban demands remains. In line with the principles of sustainable urban redevelopment, riverfront industrial zones require transformation that balances environmental, economic, and social aspects (Said and

Dindar 2024). This represents a particularly complex challenge due to layered spatial constraints, diverse functions, and the involvement of stakeholders with often conflicting interests.

Addressing this complexity requires a comprehensive understanding of urban transformation processes. In recent decades, advances in digital tools have significantly enhanced the capacity to analyse such complexity. The application of Geographic Information System (GIS) has become common in contemporary research on urban transformations, and such a system enables overcoming the fragmentation of existing approaches while also allowing the integration of remote sensing. GIS facilitates the collection and analysis of spatial, economic, and social information, which are essential for conducting complex, multi-dimensional analyses. GIS is particularly useful for identifying spatial changes by comparing cartographic and satellite data before and after the implemented transformation. At the same time, GIS enables the classification and categorization of data, supporting the systematic identification and analysis of spatial patterns and typologies (Bhadwal and Kumar 2025, Ludwig and Alvanides 2023). The application of GIS supports the integrated and standardised evaluation of changes, contributing to a better understanding of cause-and-effect relationships and spatial dynamics in the urban transformation of river areas.

However, existing evaluation approaches are frequently limited by sectoral fragmentation, focusing on isolated aspects such as land use (Pilua et al. 2025), flood resistance (Tayyab et al. 2021), or mobility (Durgut and Ozkan 2022), rather than providing a holistic assessment. Moreover, while urban regeneration has been widely studied, relatively few contributions specifically address riverfront redevelopment, and even fewer focus on the smaller cities, where spatial constraints, economic dependencies, and social dynamics differ significantly from those of larger metropolitan contexts.

This research aims to address this gap by developing a methodology for the comprehensive analysis of riverfront transformation, focusing on small and medium-sized cities, which remain insufficiently explored despite the extensive body of waterfront research.

The research also builds on the authors' previous work (Ivančan et al. 2025) in which the core criteria for evaluating the transformation of port and industrial areas were identified. That study established key conceptual criteria for port-city integration, organized into two main groups. Spatial criteria include physical accessibility, continuity of

movement, and the degree of built-up area, while functional criteria encompass land use, focal points, and social activity.

The present study aims to demonstrate that these conceptual criteria can be translated into measurable indicators and assessed using quantitative data. In doing so, it addresses a significant research gap by proposing a methodological framework for the multi-criteria evaluation of urban riverfront redevelopment, with particular emphasis on its spatial dimension and its applicability across diverse urban settings.

2 Materials and methods

OpenStreetMap (OSM) data were used as the primary spatial data source, providing consistent global mapping coverage of the entire European continent, and is regularly updated to reflect real-world changes. Using OSM ensures comparability across different urban areas while enabling the analysis of spatial transformations over time.

To ensure data measurability, conceptual spatial and functional criteria are translated into measurable indicators using OSM spatial data. The following indicators are defined:

- Physical accessibility and movement continuity: measured as the total length (in meters) of pedestrian paths, bicycle lanes, vehicular roads, service roads, and other pathways, as well as the number of public transportation stops.
- Degree of built-up area: measured as the total building footprint area in square meters.
- Land use: expressed as the percentage distribution of different land use categories, providing insight into the functional composition of the area.
- Focal points (POIs): defined as the number of points of interest, including amenities, leisure facilities, tourism points, and man-made structures.

The study focuses on the evaluation of riverfront redevelopment in two mid-sized European cities (100,000 – 250,000 inhabitants): Nijmegen in the Netherlands and Linz in Austria, selected for their urban transformation of the working riverfront.

The city of Nijmegen (187,000 inh.) is located on the river Waal. A recent initiative in the city is the Groene Delta

project (Figure 1), which aims to transform the industrial riverfront area into a hub for sustainable energy production. The project emphasizes the integration of the site into the urban fabric through the introduction of new pedestrian and cycling paths, the reuse of existing industrial structures for public facilities, and the expansion of a network of public spaces, promoting accessibility, social interaction, and active use of the riverfront.

The city of Linz (206,000 inh.) has a long history of inland transport and industry due to its location on the Danube. The Linz Hafen Master Plan aims to better integrate the riverfront into city life by improving accessibility, connectivity, and the provision of public areas. The development of Hafenpark in Linz Hafen (Figure 1.), with a new public space atop a logistics building, exemplifies this approach by creating a distinctive interface between active port functions and urban public life.

Both riverfront transformation areas were analysed at two temporal stages: 2014 (Linz) and 2015 (Nijmegen), representing the state prior to major redevelopment interventions, and 2026, capturing the outcomes of transformation processes. This enables the assessment of changes in spatial structure, land use, transport connectivity, accessibility of public space, and the distribution of POIs, thereby providing a quantitative evaluation of both spatial and functional transformations.

By integrating OSM data with a multi-criteria evaluation framework, these measurable indicators support a systematic comparison of urban structure, land use, and port-city integration before and after the transformation, while maintaining a consistent and comparable dataset across both case study cities.

3 Results

The multi-criteria, spatial-temporal GIS-based comparative analysis of two cities reveals significant spatial and functional changes following the riverfront transformation processes.

In terms of mobility networks, both Nijmegen and Linz show a clear increase in connectivity. The total length of pedestrian paths increased from 78 m to 3630 m in Nijmegen and from 1134 m to 2129 m in Linz. Similarly, cycling infrastructure expanded from 931 m to 1943 m in

Figure 1. Groene Delta (left) and Linz Hafen (right) on an OSM map, 2026.

Nijmegen and from 0 m to 16 m in Linz. The total length of vehicular and service roads also recorded changes, indicating an overall densification of the mobility network and improved permeability.

Regarding public transport accessibility, both case studies show an increase in the number of stops. In Nijmegen, the number of stops increased from 0 to 4, while in Linz it increased from 6 to 10, suggesting enhanced integration of the riverfront areas into the wider urban transport system.

The analysis of built-up areas reveals contrasting development patterns. In Linz, the built-up area increased from 8.2 ha to 8.7 ha, primarily due to the construction of a new logistics building with a publicly accessible roof. In contrast, Nijmegen experienced a decrease in built-up area from 6.4 ha to 4.1 ha, largely as a result of the removal of the former coal power plant.

The distribution of points of interest (POIs) also changed significantly. In Nijmegen, the number of POIs increased from 3 to 7, while in Linz it rose from 6 to 14. These POIs include amenities, leisure facilities, tourism-related sites, and man-made structures, indicating a growth in activity nodes and socially relevant spaces.

Although a comprehensive land-use analysis based solely on OSM data proved unreliable, it was possible to track changes in green areas within the study sites. In Nijmegen, the extent of green space increased from 1.3 ha to 5.1 ha, while in Linz it rose from 0.4 ha to 0.7 ha. These changes indicate an improvement in environmental quality and the introduction or expansion of open and recreational spaces as part of the riverfront transformation.

4 Discussion

The results indicate that both riverfront transformation areas achieved an improvement in spatial integration. However, as illustrated in the graphs (Figure 2), the degree of improvement varies across indicators, reflecting the implementation of different transformation strategies. While Linz increased its built-up density by adding new structures, Nijmegen reduced its built-up area by removing

obsolete industrial infrastructure, thereby creating more green spaces and enhancing the visual integration of the area. This contrast demonstrates that urban integration depends not solely on the level of built-up density, but also more on the quality of connectivity, accessibility, and functional diversity.

The increase in pedestrian and cycling networks, together with the higher number of public transport stops, indicates improved permeability and accessibility, key components of successful spatial integration. Additionally, the growth in POIs suggests an enhancement of the riverfront's social dimension, as these elements represent spaces for interaction, activity, and public use. The observed increase in functional diversity further supports the conclusion that both projects contribute to more inclusive and multifunctional urban environments, in line with the principles of sustainable urban regeneration.

However, several limitations were identified in the methodology, particularly in the analysis of land use using OSM data. OSM reflects existing functions rather than planned land use and, in some cases, does not consistently cover the entire study area, which reduces the reliability and precision of the results. Despite these limitations, the applied methodology demonstrates strong potential for GIS-based comparative analysis of urban transformations, particularly with regard to spatial and functional indicators of integration.

5 Conclusions

This paper demonstrates that the main criteria for riverfront integration, previously identified through theoretical research, can be effectively translated into measurable indicators and assessed with GIS-based methods. By applying a multi-criteria, spatial-temporal approach based on OSM data, it was possible to quantify spatial and functional changes and to compare transformation processes across different urban contexts and time periods.

Figure 2. Riverfront transformation indicators for Groene Delta and Linz Hafen.

The case studies of Nijmegen and Linz demonstrate that riverfront redevelopment improves the integration of formerly industrial areas into the urban fabric. This is reflected in increased connectivity, enhanced accessibility, and greater presence of socially relevant functions, such as points of interest. Importantly, the findings indicate that a higher level of integration does not necessarily depend on an increase in built-up density. While Linz intensified its built structure and Nijmegen reduced it, both achieved positive integration outcomes, highlighting the importance of mobility networks and functional diversity over purely physical development.

At the same time, the research identifies certain methodological limitations, particularly in relation to land-use analysis based on OSM data. As OSM primarily reflects recorded uses and does not consistently cover all spatial categories, it is less reliable for detailed land-use evaluation. Therefore, future research should incorporate additional data sources, such as official planning or cadastral datasets, to ensure more accurate and comprehensive analysis. Overall, the proposed methodological framework represents a step toward a more comprehensive and evidence-based evaluation of urban riverfront transformations. It enables comparative analysis across different cities and supports decision-making processes aimed at achieving more sustainable, accessible, and integrated urban environments. To enable a more holistic understanding of riverfronts, future research is planned to expand beyond urban planning perspectives to include social, economic, and ecological dimensions as well.

Acknowledgments: "The research was conducted as part of the Adaptive Urban Planning (adPLAN) project at the University of Zagreb, Faculty of Architecture, Croatia. The project received EU funding through the Croatian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) under the EU 581 Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)."

6 References

- Bhadwal, S., Kumar, M., 2025. Assessing Urban Green Infrastructure Transformation in Delhi (1991–2021): A Landscape Ecology and Remote Sensing Approach. *Asian Journal of Geographical Research* 8 (3), 1–22.
- Durgut, Z.C., Ozkan, D.Y., 2022. The Effects of Spatial Connectivity on Pedestrian Movement and Space Usage in Waterfront Areas. In: *Proceedings of the 13th Space Syntax Symposium*, Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Bergen, Norway.
- Ivančan, D., Srbljanin, E., Gašparović, S., Mrđa, A., 2025. Uloga javnih prostora u urbanističkom integriranju lučkih područja u gradove. In: *Proceedings of the X. International Conference on Industrial Heritage*, Rijeka, Croatia.
- Ludwig, C., Alvanides, S., 2023. A Spatio-Temporal Analysis of the Urban Fabric of Nuremberg From the 1940s Onwards Using Historical Maps. *Urban Planning* 8 (1).
- Mann, R., 1973. *Rivers in the City*. First ed. Henry Holt & Company, Inc., New York.
- Moccia, F.D., 2012. Port Operations and Displacement vs. Urban Redevelopment of Port Areas: Could There Be an Alternative Model of Waterfront Redevelopment for Small and Medium Port Cities Based on Port Operations? *BDC* 12, 277–288.
- Pilua, A., Kader, S., Zejnilovic, E., Tariq, A., Sestras, P., Teqja, Z., Hysa, A., 2025. Green or Grey: Investigating the urban rivers' landscapes along the capital cities of Western Balkans. *European Planning Studies*.
- Said, Z.M., Dindar, S., 2024. Key Challenges and Strategies in the Evaluation of Sustainable Urban Regeneration Projects: Insights from a Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability* 16 (22), 9903.
- Tayyab, M., Zhang, J., Hussain, M., Ullah, S., Liu, X., Khan, S.N., Baig, M.A., Hassan, W., Al-Shaibah, B., 2021. GIS-Based Urban Flood Resilience Assessment Using Urban Flood Resilience Model: A Case Study of Peshawar City, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *Remote Sensing* 13 (10), 1864.